

Methods on teaching English as a second language

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Abstract: This article demonstrate the methods of teaching English and conducting the lesson in an interesting way. From this article, you can learn types of the methods and their examples.

Key words: direct method, grammar translation method, audio-lingual method, suggestopedia.

Introduction: The methodology of teaching English differ from person to person. A teacher in a classroom with 25-50 students, the sole speaker striking facts and theories at the students, is the traditional teaching method. Like any other topic, teaching language has undergone many changes. It has shifted to role-plays, interactive games, short visuals, etc. from the traditional ways. Teaching a language has different ways and paradigms. Let's look at some of the most effective and popular methods of teaching English. There are very famous and productive methods of teaching English. Some popular methods are Grammar-cum-Translation, Direct Method, Audio-Lingual, Suggestopedia, and Silent Way.

In the history of teaching languages, there are many teaching approaches and techniques, with some being more well-known and successful than others. Language teaching methods are reliant on and affected by various hypotheses of language learning. The historical backdrop of language teaching advances in multiple ways. There are a lot of methods of English teaching, and we've listed a few that are very famous and active methods.

1. Grammar-cum-Translation Method
2. The Direct Method
3. The Audio-Lingual Method
4. Suggestopedia
5. The Silent Way
6. Total Physical Response

Grammar -Translation Method

The name itself explains the functionality of the grammar-cum-translation method. The strategy of teaching English in grammar orientation depends on a ton of interpretation. The technique is the conventional or 'old style' method of learning a language. A few nations approach this teaching style. The fundamental thought behind this strategy is that the students become familiar with all grammar rules to translate various sentences easily. Many teachers recognize this technique as incapable since it does not include the spoken form of the language, and communication skills are ignored. Furthermore, it does not allow the learners to think directly in the target language. Thus, it hinders the creation of a direct link between thoughts and expression. Consequently, this technique doesn't

improve the student's communicative ability in the language but only builds strong language writing skills.

The Direct Method

The Audio method is also known as the direct method, which involves thinking and speaking in English. Here the communication between the teacher and the student is strictly in English, and the student is barred from using their native language. This way, the student can get a stronghold on the accent and fluency, the frequency of grammatical errors in this would be less. This method is widely used as it helps the students learn the English language in a way a native English speaker would speak like and not the orthodox textbook way. The following principle and procedures that guide the natural method are: Teachers and students both use the target language in the classroom, students tend to have daily sessions on vocabulary and sentences, grammar is instructed inductively.

The Audio-Lingual Method

The audio-lingual method is also recognized as the Army Method. During the first world war, the American Armed forces started escalating oral courses known as the 'Military particular Training Program' (ASTP). Instructive organizations later received it as the audio-lingual method. The striking highlights of the audio-lingual method are: Language teaching starts with communication; the material is educated before it is offered in composed structure. The objective language is the study hall's main language; the students' primary language isn't utilized. The teacher is the role model for the student; student-to-student interaction happens in chain drills.

Suggestopedia

Suggestopedia is a behaviourist theory developed by Georgi Lozanov, the Bulgarian psychotherapist in the 1970s. The method involves using the environment, music, decoratives, etc., for learning the language. It depends a lot on the atmosphere and the physical environmental factors of the class. When teachers prepare to utilize the Suggestopedia method, there's a great deal of craftsmanship and music included. Each suggestopedia exercise is divided into three unique stages: Deciphering, Concert Session, Elaboration

The Silent Way

The silent way leans mainly on the student's self-sufficiency. The teacher demonstrates only as a facilitator attempting to urge students to be more efficient in their learning. The fundamental of these lines of teaching is for the teacher to state practically nothing so that students can assume responsibility for their education.

Total Physical Response

Total Physical Response, also called TPR, is a methodology that follows 'learning by doing. For example, apprentices will learn English through a series of activities, "Close the door", "Stand up", "Open your book", and "Stroll to the window and open it." With TPR, the most significant aptitude is aural perception, and everything else will be regular.

Reference

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- An example of a task-based activity could be to have each student draw a comic picture and explain the content and the inspiration behind it to the group. They then have to collaborate to put together a comic strip that includes each student's picture, which is the main task (to create an original comic strip).